

SCHOOL HEADS' HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT PRACTICES, TEACHERS' SCHOOL ENGAGEMENT, AND TEACHING PERFORMANCE

Rowell Genopanon Olaivar ¹

¹ Human Resource Director, Human Resource Management and Development Office, Bohol Northern Star College, Ubay, Bohol, Philippines

² School President, Bohol Northern Star College, Ubay, Bohol, Philippines

Received 04 August 2022
Accepted 05 September 2022
Published 23 September 2022

Corresponding Author

Rowell Genopanon Olaivar,
rowell.olaivar@bnsc.edu.ph

DOI [10.29121/granthaalayah.v10.i9.2022.4758](https://doi.org/10.29121/granthaalayah.v10.i9.2022.4758)

Funding: This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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ABSTRACT

The main thrust of the study was to evaluate the school heads' human resource management (HRM) practices in relation to teachers' school engagement and teaching performance. The study employed a descriptive survey method. It was conducted among the 55 private elementary schools in the Division of Bohol using modified questionnaire checklists from [Khan N. \(2015\)](#), [Klassen et al. \(2012\)](#), and [the Education Manpower Bureau \(2003\)](#). The Spearman Rank Correlation Coefficient determined the relationship between variables, while the p-value tested the significance level. With the sudden shift in the educational landscape, school heads' HRM practices, teachers' school engagement, and teaching performance among private schools have not shown an interdependent relationship since their p-values 0.846, 0.103, and 0.178, respectively, are greater than the 0.05 level of significance. Teachers have independently performed their duties and responsibilities in the new normal setup regardless of the intervention of their school heads. School heads' human resource management practices have not been associated with teachers' school engagement and teaching performance. Hence, the researcher recommends that the Board of Directors (BODs), owners, and school heads of private elementary schools should maintain the high practice of the human resource management policies and procedures with more emphasis on the compensation and reward management and conduct of professional developmental activities for teachers regarding modular distance learning delivery modality. Moreover, teachers should maintain school engagement, focusing more on the issues they met in implementing modular distance learning, like student cheating. They should design an anti-cheating scheme regarding the answering of learning modules. Also, teachers should safeguard their mental health as they carry out their roles and responsibilities as curriculum implementers in the new normal. In terms of teaching performance, teachers should stress more on providing support to their students to ensure quality learning despite the absence of face-to-face interaction between them and their students.

Keywords: School Heads' Human Resource Management Practices, Teachers' School Engagement, Teaching Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

Human resource management practices play a vital role in catering to the needs and assessing the performance of an organization's unique and diverse important asset, the human capital. As a social institution tasked to gear up people with the

knowledge and skills necessary to adjust to this ever-changing society, schools must consider implementing their respective human resource management practices among their teachers to ensure optimum school engagement and commendable teaching performance are met. Therefore, a particular strategic practice/s of human resource management should be established and harnessed with teachers' performance in attaining efficient, quality, and globally competitive education.

According to [Noe et al. \(2018\)](#), an organization performs best when all these practices are managed well. Employees and customers at schools with effective HRM tend to be more satisfied, and the companies tend to be more innovative, have greater productivity, and develop a more favourable reputation in the community.

With the sudden shift in the educational landscape brought by the COVID-19 pandemic, private schools have quickly ventured into the "unknown unknowns" as they strive to help their workforce adapt to and cope with radical changes occurring in the work social environment. Teachers' school engagement has been affected due to limited face-to-face interaction among stakeholders and the skeletal workforce scheme. Moreover, teaching performance might be adjusted due to shelter-in-place orders and remote working conditions. This has likely further limited the segmentation between work and private spheres leading to more significant difficulties in "unplugging" from work demands [Chawla et al. \(2020\)](#).

Hence, it is within this premise that the researcher found great interest in investigating the level of School Heads' Human Resource Management Practices, Teachers' School Engagement, and Teaching performance which may eventually benefit the school heads/administrators and improve teaching engagement and performance of teachers in the selected private elementary schools of the Division of Bohol.

1.1. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The main thrust of the study was to determine the level of school heads' human resource management practices in relation to teachers' school engagement and teaching performance in private elementary schools of the Division of Bohol for the school year 2020-2021.

2. HYPOTHESIS

- 1) There is no significant relationship between the school heads' human resource management practices as perceived by the teachers and school heads themselves and the level of teachers' school engagement; level of teaching performance as perceived by the school heads and teachers themselves.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between the level of teachers' school engagement and teaching performance as perceived by the school heads and teachers themselves.

3. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized a descriptive survey in gathering data for analysis and interpretation. Quantitative data from the survey checklist were used to develop a comprehensive picture of the research problem. The inferential research design was employed to determine the relationship between human resource management practices, teachers' school engagement, and teaching performance.

3.1. ENVIRONMENT AND PARTICIPANTS

The Division of Bohol is the locale of the study. It is composed of 55 private elementary schools clustered into three congressional districts. Each school is governed/ supervised by a principal. The study respondents were the selected school heads and teachers at private elementary schools in I, II, and III Congressional Districts of the Division of Bohol for the school year 2020-2021. There were 409 respondents comprising 58 school heads and 351 teachers. These were chosen through the convenience sampling method. Moreover, the only school with four teachers and above participated in the rating. [Table 1](#)

4. RESULTS

Table 1

Table 1 What are the overall levels of school heads' human resource management practices perceived by the teachers and school heads?

Areas	WM	D	Rank
1.1 Recruitment and Selection	3.85	HP	1
1.2 Training and Development	3.71	HP	4
1.3 Compensation and Reward Management	3.51	HP	5
1.4 Promotion Practices	3.76	HP	2.5
1.5 Performance Appraisal	3.76	HP	2.5
Overall Mean	3.72	HP	

As shown, among the five areas, recruitment, and selection of school heads' HRM practices perceived by the teachers and school heads got the highest weighted mean of 3.85, described as "Highly Practiced." It means that school heads, as human resource managers, have highly practiced good recruitment & selection processes.

Section 62, School Recruitment Policy, of DepEd Order No. 88, s.2010 or the 2010 Revised Manual of Regulations for Private Schools in Basic Education specifies each private school shall have a policy on recruitment, selection, and appointment of its school personnel, subject to the salary and qualification standards and other conditions of employment as provided for by law in this Manual. Thus, the private school's selection committee shall interview applicants and ensure that all have equal opportunities to be assessed.

Hence, school heads must continuously design proper recruitment and selection devices to increase the probability that the right person is chosen to fill a slot, when the right people are selected for the job, productivity increases.

On the other hand, compensation and reward management got the lowest weighted mean of 3.51, interpreted as "Highly Practiced." It means private schools still compensate teachers with the same remuneration before and during modular distance learning, where they render duties in a skeletal working scheme.

A study by [Mauno et al. \(2016\)](#) showed that engaged employees are highly self-efficacious; they believe they can meet the demands they face in various contexts. Besides, engaged workers tend to think that they will generally experience good outcomes in life (optimistic) and believe they can satisfy their needs by participating in organizational-based self-esteem.

On the other hand, if not motivated, highly skilled employees may become poor performers, and for better performance, they necessitate rewards [Delaney and](#)

[Hussield \(2018\)](#). The reward system boosts performance and efficiency in both the employee's and the organization's best interests.

Hence, better reward and performance-related compensation systems must be designed to improve an employee's performance, improving the organization's productivity.

Overall, school heads' human resource management practices perceived by the teachers and school heads were rated 3.72, described as "Highly Practiced." This signifies that school heads in private elementary schools have demonstrated their existing human resource management policies and procedures. These policies include recruitment and selection, training and development, compensation and reward management, promotion practices, and performance appraisal. [Table 2](#)

Table 2

Table 2 What are the overall levels of teachers' school engagement?			
Terms	WM	D	Rank
2.1 Cognitive Engagement	3.94	VME	1
2.2 Emotional Engagement	3.81	VME	7
2.3 Behavioural Engagement	3.87	VME	3.5
2.4 Social Engagement with:			
2.4.1 Co-teachers	3.83	VME	6
2.4.2 Pupils	3.90	VME	2
2.4.3 School Head	3.84	VME	5
2.4.4 Parents	3.87	VME	3.5
Overall Mean	3.87	VME	

It can be inferred that among the four indicators, teacher-respondents rated cognitive engagement with the highest weighted mean of 3.94, "Very Much Engaged." This signifies that teachers tried their best to perform and discharge their school duties and responsibilities, specifically in implementing the school curriculum during these trying times. As [Staiger \(2018\)](#) said, effective teaching depends on teachers who are cognitively motivated in his/her work. The result further entails that teachers are open-minded about their learners' differences. Having diverse learners is an extra challenge and effort on the part of teachers, yet teachers are versatile to give all the best they can just to cope with the 21st-century learners' needs.

Although rated the least weighted mean of 3.81, "Very Much Engaged," the teachers' emotional engagement remained high. This means teachers are emotionally stable during the new normal in education as they perform their daily tasks in school or work from home. This further entails that teachers were able to overcome the emotional baggage they encountered due to the sudden shift in learning delivery modality.

In the overall, teachers' level of engagement was rated 3.87, described as "Very Much Engaged." This signifies that teacher perceived themselves as motivated individuals who devotedly discharged their duties and responsibilities expected of them as curriculum implementers in the new normal. This further depicts that their relationship with their colleagues, parents, and students remained steady even during the absence of face-to-face interaction.

[Porter and Brophy \(2018\)](#) posited that effective teachers demonstrate their commitment to teaching by accepting responsibility for pupil learning and behaviour. They added further that genuine interest in education and enthusiasm

for learning are essential characteristics of effective teachers. However, [Durksen and Klassen \(2017\)](#) proved that global teacher engagement changes over even a brief period of time in starting teachers, with a commitment to the profession mirroring the pattern of change in engagement. [Table 3](#)

Table 3

Table 3 What do the school heads and teachers perceive overall levels of teachers' teaching performance?			
Terms	WM	D	Rank
3.1 Curriculum Implementation	3.84	0	2
3.2 Teaching Strategies and Skills	3.82	0	4
3.3 Knowledge and Attitude	3.80	0	5.5
3.4 Assessment Planning and Implementation	3.80	0	5.5
3.5 Support for Student Development	3.79	0	7
3.6 Links with Parents and External Organizations	3.83	0	3
3.7 Interpersonal Relationship	3.92	0	1
Overall Mean	3.83	0	

Among the seven (7) indicators, the teacher exemplified best in an interpersonal relationship with the highest weighted mean of 3.92, described as "Outstanding." This result coincides with the finding in the preceding table, which shows that teachers have established positive social engagement with their colleagues at work. Thus, despite the limited face-to-face interaction, teachers have still found ways to connect with the people within the school or work from home.

[Hargreaves et al. \(2018\)](#) claimed that positive interpersonal relationships with colleagues, students, parents, and other stakeholders have significantly better chances of reaching an outstanding performance level. So, the quality of teaching and learning is affected by the quality of professional relationships that occur outside of the classroom. When a professional teaching culture is present, sustainable change and increased learning opportunities are more likely to occur.

[Mitchell et al. \(2018\)](#) affirm that interpersonal skills are a robust prognosticator of business and professional triumph as well as an indicator of a decrease in organizational success and problem-solving.

Further, having positive interpersonal skills upsurges the yield in the organization since the number of conflicts is reduced. In an informal situation, it permits communication to be calm and pleased. People with good interpersonal skills can generally control 152 feelings that arise in challenging conditions and retort appropriately instead of being overwhelmed by emotion.

Meanwhile, support for student development got the lowest weighted mean of 3.79, described as "Outstanding." But this still suggests that teachers have demonstrated enough support for developing their students who are geographically distant from them. Conduct of monitoring through texts and phone calls is one-way teachers extend help to their students.

According to [Tshwane University of Technology \(TUT\) \(2018\)](#), support for student development includes career counselling, study counselling, language development programs, information literacy, personal skills and social skills development, and supportive services among students.

In the overall, teaching performance as perceived by the school heads and teachers themselves was rated 3.83, interpreted as "Outstanding." This finding suggests that teachers have shown commendable performance based on their duties

and responsibilities. These duties cover implementing the school curriculum, establishing community linkage, and supporting student welfare. Furthermore, all items in the teaching performance questionnaire are very doable by teachers since these are the essential and required roles that are expected of them to perform. Hence, most of them have high performance since private schools require these skills. More so, no tasks in the questionnaires are beyond the minimum job requirements of a teacher, all are minimum and achievable by them.

A study by [Patricia \(2018\)](#) states that the performance of members of any organization depends on the ability to effectively interact with their superiors, subordinates, and co-workers within the organization and consumers, suppliers, and the general public outside.

5. HYPOTHESES

Table 4

Table 4 Relationship Among Variables				
Variables	Spearman rho test	p-value	Interpretation	Decision
1. School Heads' Human Resource Management Practices and Teachers' School Engagement	-0.026	0.846	Not Related	Insignificant, Ho: Accepted
2. School Heads' Human Resource Management Practices and Teachers' Teaching Performance	-0.216	0.103	Not Related	Insignificant, Ho: Accepted
3. Teachers' School Engagement and Teaching Performance	0.179	0.178	Not Related	Insignificant, Ho: Accepted

[Table 4](#) depicts the relationship among variables. As shown, there is no significant relationship between the school heads' human resource management practice and teachers' school engagement because the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. It can be assumed that due to the absence or limited face-to-face interaction between the school heads and teachers brought by the pandemic, the human resource management skills that the school heads practiced did not seem to influence the teachers' school engagement. Furthermore, these human resource management practices did not directly affect the modified roles of teachers under distance learning due to some changes in their customary tasks.

[Kristof-Brown and Guay \(2018\)](#) affirms the finding of the present study, which states that dramatic alterations in how and where employees do their work is likely to have important implications for employees' experiences of person-environment fit (P-E fit) or the level of congruence between the attributes they possess and those of the environment. P-E fit theory posits that individuals are attracted to and selected by organizations whose work environments reflect the same values, cultures, and features as their essential beliefs, values, and desires [Kristof-Brown and Guay \(2018\)](#).

However, the finding contradicts the study of [Fahim \(2018\)](#) that school heads' human resource management practices lead to higher commitment and engagement and limit the voluntary leave of employees, and therefore, can be used to predict the teacher's turnover rate.

[Yao et al. \(2019\)](#). also claimed that psychological and social factors and variables such as interaction and schoolwork engagement could effectively increase employee retention and productivity. Thus, organizations need to engage teachers

to leverage their talent; this can be the culture at organizations to nurture talent and raise human potential.

In consonance, [Shibiti \(2020\)](#) described that effective human resource management practices could influence teachers' schoolwork engagement levels, improve the client's service quality, satisfaction, and retention, offer a distinctive competitive advantage, and improve the organization's performance and success. Hence, the greater the human resource management practices, the better the school engagement, and vice versa.

As illustrated in the same table, there is no significant relationship between school heads' human resource management practices and teachers' teaching performance since the p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. Statistically, due to the abrupt and radical changes occurring in the work and social environment, the human resource management skills that the school heads have practiced did not seem to be a contributing factor to teachers' teaching performance. Moreover, these human resource management practices did not directly relate to the performance of teachers amidst the quick adjustment to remote working conditions, such as shifting to remote environments and decreasing the value and interest of one's work.

The result abates the study of [Selamat et al. \(2018\)](#), which found out that the employees' high satisfaction with the management effectiveness equates to an increase in their job productivity, and the study of [Akinfolarin and Emetarom \(2017\)](#), which viewed that management support practices are geared towards providing a friendly climate for workers' productivity.

[Majumder \(2017\)](#) also contradicts strong relationships between HRM practices and employee satisfaction in Bangladesh private organizations, and [Kim and Lee \(2017\)](#) found evidence that HRM policies and practices improve strategic capabilities and firm performance in management consultant firms in South Korea. The study by [Demo \(2016\)](#) showed a positive and robust relationship between HRM policies and employee performance.

As manifested in the same table, the overall p-value is greater than the 0.05 level of significance; thus, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means there is no significant relationship between teachers' school engagement and teaching performance. The teachers' school engagement has nothing to do with their teaching performance.

According to [Klassen et al. \(2012\)](#), teachers' school engagement refers to their solid professional relationships with their school heads, co-teachers, students, and parents. This covers cognitive, emotional, behavioral, and social engagement with co-teachers, pupils, school heads, and parents. On the other hand, teaching performance refers to the continuous process of identifying, evaluating, and developing teachers' work performance to ensure that the school will effectively achieve goals and objectives. This includes curriculum implementation, teaching strategies and skills, knowledge and attitude, assessment planning and implementation, support for student development, linkage with parents and external organizations, and interpersonal relationship [Education Manpower Bureau \(2003\)](#).

Due to the sudden shift in the educational landscape brought about by the COVID-19 pandemic, both teachers' school engagement and teaching performance have been affected. Thus, it can be inferred that the interdependent relationship between these two variables has also changed.

This finding rebuts the study of [Kilgallon et al. \(2018\)](#), which claimed that identified personal factors such as knowledge and attitudes, support for student development, interpersonal relationships, and well-being of the individual teachers had influenced teachers' school engagement levels, which eventually impacted on the overall teachers' performance level.

The finding further contradicts the study of [Porter and Lawler \(2018\)](#), which states that effective teachers demonstrate their commitment to teaching by accepting responsibility for pupil learning and behavior.

In symmetry, a study by [Mauno et al. \(2016\)](#) showed that engaged employees are highly self-efficacious; they believe they can meet the demands they face in various contexts. In addition, engaged workers tend to think that they will generally experience good outcomes in life (optimistic) and can satisfy their needs by participating in roles within the organization (organizational-based self-esteem). Thus, if teachers are well-engaged, their performance relative to academic aspects in school (e.g., curriculum implementation) yields positive results.

To sum up, the findings of the study could give input to the Board of Directors, Trustees, owners, and the Department of Education on the importance of school heads' human resource management practices, teachers' school engagement, and teaching performance in carrying out the curriculum implementation of the private schools amid pandemics.

Finally, since it was found out that school heads' human resource management practices do not affect teachers' school engagement and teaching performance, it would be vital advocacy of the Bohol Association of Private Elementary Administrators, Directors, and Owners to strengthen the implementation of their existing HRM policies and procedures to respond to the needs of the time. These policies should further consider the best interest of the teachers who served as the frontliners in the basic education learning continuity amid the COVID-19 pandemic.

6. CONCLUSION

The essence of a human resource manager in any organization can never be compromised nor disregarded. In the study, private elementary school heads demonstrated commendable human resource management skills under the new normal where the customary face-to-face learning delivery mode has been replaced with a modular learning approach. In the same vein, teachers still exemplified outstanding performance and school engagement despite the new learning delivery modality implemented in their respective schools.

With the sudden shift in the educational landscape, school heads' human resource management practices, teachers' school engagement, and teaching performance among private schools have not shown an interdependent relationship. Teachers have independently performed their duties and responsibilities in the new normal setup regardless of the intervention of their school heads. School heads' human resource management practices have not been associated with teachers' school engagement and teaching performance.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based upon the findings and conclusions of the study, the following recommendations were drawn:

- 1) The Board of Directors (BODs), Trustees, owners, and school heads of the private elementary schools should maintain a high practice of the human

resource management policies and procedures with more emphasis on the compensation and reward management and conduct of professional developmental activities for teachers regarding modular distance learning delivery modality.

- 2) Teachers should maintain their school engagement, focusing more on the issues met by them in implementing modular distance learning, like the concern of the authenticity and veracity of students' responses in answering the printed modules. They should design an authentication and verification scheme for answering learning modules. Also, teachers should safeguard their mental health as they carry out their roles and responsibilities as curriculum implementers in the new normal.
- 3) In terms of teaching performance, teachers should stress more on the provision of support to their students to ensure quality learning despite the absence of face-to-face interaction between them and their students.
- 4) Future researchers may conduct a parallel study regarding the school heads' human resource management practices, teachers' school engagement, and teaching performance among public schools to compare the status of these types of schools under the new normal situation.

CONFLICT OF INTERESTS

None.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

None.

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